

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

PERFORMANCE INDICATORS TO SUPPORT REMOTE WORKING MANAGEMENT [SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 7

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PERFORMANCE INDICATORS TO SUPPORT REMOTE WORKING MANAGEMENT

The performance measurement indicators related to remote working (hereafter, RW) must focus on two perspectives:

- 1. Performance of RW from the company's perspective**
- 2. Performance of RW from the worker's perspective**

These combined indicators provide a comprehensive view from both the corporate and employee perspectives, balancing productivity and well-being.

As part of the academic POC Project MASPLIT (Methodology and Application for managing the Performance of remote work in mountainous areas), the indicators for both perspectives are identified, together with the application of the Activity-Based Costing methodology. The aim is to develop a model to optimize the management of on-site and remote work based on the performance analysis of the activities carried out and worker satisfaction.

Below, the indicators for the first perspective are briefly outlined. The goal is to offer a set of KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) from which the company can choose the ones most suitable for its reality to monitor the performance of work done in RW compared to work done at the company's premises.

COMPANY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

The RW performance indicators related to the company must address the following aspects:

1. Productivity
2. Efficiency
3. Communication and collaboration
4. Engagement

1. Productivity

The RW productivity indicators should focus on the following four themes:

- Number of tasks completed
- Quality of work
- Achievement of objectives
- Meeting deadlines

Below, each of the four themes is briefly described, and specific indicators are identified for each.

Number of tasks completed

This is a classic way of measuring productivity and is based on the number of tasks completed relative to the established work plan. It can be measured daily, weekly, or monthly.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- $\text{Number of tasks completed in RW} / \text{Number of tasks assigned in RW}$.
- $\text{Number of tasks completed on-site} / \text{Number of tasks assigned on-site}$.
- $\text{Percentage of task completion in RW} / 100$.
- $\text{Percentage of task completion on-site} / 100$.

Measurement tool: Project management software (e.g., Trello, Asana, Jira).

Quality of work

It's not enough to just complete tasks; the quality of the output must also be evaluated. This can be measured through periodic reviews, feedback from supervisors or clients, and adherence to pre-established quality standards.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- $\text{Percentage of tasks completed without errors in RW} / \text{Total tasks completed in RW}$.

- Percentage of tasks completed without errors on-site / Total tasks completed on-site.
- Number of tasks done in RW that meet quality standards / Total tasks completed in RW.
- Number of tasks done on-site that meet quality standards / Total tasks completed on-site.
- Rating received from the client on tasks done in RW (from 1 to 7).
- Rating received from the client on tasks done on-site (from 1 to 7).
- Rating received from supervisors on tasks done in RW (from 1 to 7).
- Rating received from supervisors on tasks done on-site (from 1 to 7).

Measurement tool: Periodic reviews, qualitative evaluations, feedback from internal/external clients via questionnaires.

Achievement of objectives

The company may have defined not only specific tasks but also broader objectives to achieve.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme, referring to a work period during which RW was used, are as follows:

- Percentage of key results achieved / Pre-established objectives.
- Rating received from supervisors (from 1 to 7).
- Rating received from the internal client (from 1 to 7).

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme, referring to a work period without RW, are as follows:

- Percentage of key results achieved / Pre-established objectives.
- Rating received from supervisors (from 1 to 7).
- Rating received from the internal client (from 1 to 7).

Measurement tool: Supervisor evaluation, internal evaluations, feedback from internal clients, OKR (objectives and key results) monitoring software (e.g., Lattice, Perdo).

Meeting deadlines

This involves measuring whether and how often a worker completes a task or project within the set deadline.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- Number of projects completed within the expected timeframe / Total number of projects (period without RW).
- Number of projects completed within the expected timeframe / Total number of projects (period with RW).
- Number of tasks completed within the expected timeframe / Number of tasks assigned (period without RW).
- Number of tasks completed within the expected timeframe / Number of tasks assigned (period with RW).
- Number of days of delay accumulated during the period with RW on assigned projects or tasks compared to the same period the previous year without RW.
- Completed project phase / Planned project phase.
- Actual project completion percentage / Planned project completion percentage.

Measurement tool: Project management software, project timesheets, task timesheets.

2. Efficiency

The RW efficiency indicators must focus on the following three themes:

- Time spent per task
- Use of company resources

- Number of errors or rework

Below, the three themes are briefly described, and specific indicators are identified for each.

Time spent per task

Efficiency can be measured by evaluating the average time spent to complete a task compared to the planned time.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme during a work period when RW was used are as follows:

- Time spent on a task / Estimated time.
- Total available time / Number of tasks completed.
- Total time spent on all tasks / Total estimated time for all tasks.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme during a work period without RW are as follows:

- Time spent on a task / Estimated time.
- Total available time / Number of tasks completed.
- Total time spent on all tasks / Total estimated time for all tasks.

Measurement tool: Time tracking software (e.g., Toggl, Clockify).

Use of company resources

This measures how well a worker uses the tools and resources at their disposal, such as software, hardware, and collaboration platforms, during RW.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- Number of weekly uses of key tools / Total number of expected uses.
- Monthly frequency of key tool usage / Available usage.

- Monthly intensity of key tool usage / Available usage.

Measurement tool: Analysis of software and digital resource usage (e.g., Microsoft 365 or Google Workspace usage reports).

Number of errors or rework

This measures how many errors are made or how much time is spent correcting completed work.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- Number of errors detected monthly during RW / Annual average of monthly errors.
- Number of errors detected monthly without RW / Annual average of monthly errors.
- Number of errors detected during RW / Number of tasks completed.
- Number of errors detected on-site / Number of tasks completed.
- Number of tasks completed without errors during RW / Number of tasks completed.
- Number of tasks completed without errors on-site / Number of tasks completed.

Measurement tool: Supervisor feedback, error reports.

3. Communication and collaboration

The RW indicators related to communication and collaboration should focus on the following three themes:

- Active participation in meetings
- Response time to internal communications
- Involvement in team projects

Below, the three themes are briefly described, and specific indicators are identified for each.

Active participation in meetings

This involves monitoring not only attendance at meetings but also the worker's active contribution during these sessions.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- Number of absences from online meetings / Number of online meetings held.
- Number of absences from on-site meetings / Number of on-site meetings held.
- Number of active contributions in online meetings / Number of online meetings attended.
- Number of active contributions in on-site meetings / Number of on-site meetings attended.

Measurement tool: Meeting recordings, feedback from participants.

Response time to internal communications

A useful indicator is the average response time to emails, messages, or requests on platforms like Microsoft Teams or Zoom.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- Average response time to messages in RW / Expected standard response time.
- Average response time to messages on-site / Expected standard response time.
- Number of messages received in RW / Annual average of weekly (or monthly) messages received.
- Number of messages received on-site / Annual average of weekly (or monthly) messages received.
- Number of responses to messages with positive feedback in RW / Number of responses sent in RW.
- Number of responses to messages with positive feedback on-site / Number of responses sent on-site.

Measurement tool: Internal communication software (e.g., Teams, Zoom).

Involvement in team projects

This measures how actively a worker participates in group activities by providing ideas or completing parts of shared projects.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- Number of significant contributions to team projects during RW / Total number of team projects.
- Number of significant contributions to team projects on-site / Total number of team projects.
- Positive feedback received in team projects / Total number of team projects.

Measurement tool: Feedback from team members, monitoring of contributions in projects.

4. Engagement

The RW engagement indicators should focus on the following two themes:

- 360° feedback (from colleagues and supervisors)
- Participation in company events or online training

Below, the two themes are briefly described, and specific indicators are identified for each.

360° feedback (from colleagues and supervisors)

This involves gathering feedback from multiple perspectives to evaluate the worker's attitude, productivity, and collaboration ability.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- Sum of feedback scores during RW / Number of feedbacks received during RW.
- Sum of feedback scores during on-site work / Number of feedbacks received during on-site work.

- Monthly average feedback score received / Annual average feedback score received.

Measurement tool: Internal feedback surveys, questionnaires.

Participation in company events or online training

This measures the worker's willingness to participate in training sessions or company meetings that are not strictly necessary but contribute to professional growth.

The KPIs that can be used to measure this theme are as follows:

- Number of online training courses attended / Number of available online training courses.
- Number of on-site training courses attended / Number of available on-site training courses.
- Number of online company events attended / Total number of online company events held.
- Number of on-site company events attended / Total number of on-site company events held.
- Number of training hours utilized / Total working hours.

Measurement tool: Attendance register.